

“Living is a career, do you know what I mean?”

Young-Onset Dementia and
Women’s Career Development:
PhD Summary

Rachel Allen

This short report summarises my PhD research about young-onset dementia and women's career development. My PhD was supervised by Professor Louise Ritchie and Dr Emma Bolger.

I interviewed 12 women living with young-onset dementia about their careers. Interviews were mainly online and used object elicitation; at the beginning of each interview the woman I was interviewing told me about an object they had chosen to represent their career. Careers included paid work but other roles and activities were also important.

The full thesis will be available online via the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) website. If you would like more detail about the study or have any questions, please get in touch by email (rachel.allen@uws.ac.uk) or [LinkedIn](#).

Researchers can analyse interview data in different ways. I chose a method called Reflexive Thematic Analysis, developed by Virginia Braun and Victoria Clarke.

This method of analysis enabled me to think about the data and analyse it using creative approaches. The analysis was completed in phases. I used crochet, collage, modelling, poetry and drawing during the process.

I created and shared a crochet poster at the UWS Research Festival in 2024. After each interview, I crocheted a line to help me process what I had understood and heard. I then sewed all the lines onto fabric, allowing me to feel and see the interviews as well as reading the transcripts.

This is a picture of a crochet poster that I presented at the UWS Research Festival in 2024.

My analysis was detailed through two key themes: The Career Tree and Dementia Peers and Professionals.

Each theme had several sections, shown in the picture below:

This is a visual representation of the two major themes, sub-themes and sections of my analysis.

The Career Tree

- Developing young-onset dementia meant participants needed to work differently, for example several had left paid employment and found this very difficult
- The period after diagnosis could be experienced as a 'void of dementia', a negative time of adjusting to the diagnosis whilst managing the impact on career
- Purpose helped participants to continue their careers in ways that mattered and were enjoyable to them
- For participants, young-onset dementia necessitated a transition in career priorities and a need to understand dementia alongside their individual experiences

Dementia Peers and Professionals

- Peer support was highly valued by participants. Support from others living with a diagnosis was of significant importance
- Age wasn't a very important factor when defining peers. Peers were those sharing equal status and honesty with participants
- Career experiences are relevant to the provision of dementia-related support. It was important for participants that meetings and support groups allowed them to learn and utilise their skills and abilities
- By appreciating the impact of dementia on career, interactions with clinicians and other dementia-related professionals could be more positive and helpful to women experiencing symptoms

This is me with a poster I created as I was planning the research.

From my analysis, I developed four key findings

1

Women with young-onset dementia continue their careers in different ways after they are diagnosed. However, diagnosis is a significant disruption to career, so whilst careers continue they are not continuous.

Career is not 'lost' after developing dementia, but it does not carry on as it did before. Women living with dementia at younger age need to be able to work differently, adjust priorities and enabled to contribute in ways that are purposeful and accessible to them.

2

Dementia can change career-related feelings and needs, and these feelings and needs continue to evolve after diagnosis. Feelings and needs related to dementia aren't fixed and do change.

It was important to participants that others treated them "the same", whilst also recognising they may need to be treated differently, for example with sensitivity to their dementia symptoms. Flexibility is needed in respect of both practical considerations and emotional wellbeing.

3

Women living with young-onset dementia gain benefit from support that incorporates career-related needs and experiences.

Offering support in forms familiar to and comfortable for participants of working age can support continued growth and learning, as well as opportunities to meet and engage with others. Participants shared differing and various examples of support they had received or been part of, evidencing the importance of considering individual needs.

4

Connecting with peers who enable career aspirations and continuance after diagnosis is important.

Peers can be important source of encouragement and enablers of career for women living with young-onset dementia. Participants who had connected with peers, for example through support or advocacy groups, spoke positively about these experiences and the helpful impact of peers on their career. There was recognition of the benefits of meeting together with other women and the importance of sharing life stage or interests.

Recommendations

For Research:

- Further research is needed, for example to explore men's experiences and how careers are impacted by specific types of dementia
- Other researchers can learn from this study about ways they can use creative approaches as part of their work
- Object elicitation and online interviews can be effectively used in dementia-focused research

For Career Guidance:

- 'Career' is often synonymous with paid employment, so it is important that the inclusion of non-paid activities is part of communication about career guidance
- As career-related feelings and needs change when living with dementia, positive and person-centred support needs to be dynamically flexible

For Policy:

- Career guidance professionals should be considered as part of the 'dementia workforce' (professionals supporting people living with a diagnosis)
- The Scottish Government could include insights from this study in the delivery plan for Scotland's Dementia Strategy

This is an artwork I created for the Alzheimer's Association International Conference (AIC) in 2024. You can read more about this online: <https://alz-journals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/alz.084014>

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